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Endogean and cavernicolous Coleoptera of the Balkans. XXVI. Two new species of *Ubychia* Rost, 1893 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Raymondionyminae) from Croatia and Romania

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SUMMARY. Two new species of the endogean weevil genus *Ubychia* Rost, 1893 (*U. jansai* sp. n. from Croatia and *U. romanica* sp. n. from Romania) are described and illustrated. The key to the Balkanic species of the genus with hexamerous antennal funicle is provided. The distribution of the genus is briefly discussed. Maps of the distribution of all *Ubychia* species are given.

KEY WORDS: Balkan, distribution, endogean weevils, Mediterranean region, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Raymondionymini, as currently composed, is a small tribe of the curculionid family Brachyceridae with 16 genera and 94 species (Morrone & Hlaváč 2017 and subsequent descriptions) with the centre of the radiation in the western Palaearctic region, especially the Mediterranean region (9 genera / 76 species). The rest of tribe is known from western USA (3/5), Mexico (2/2) Madagascar (1/3) and Venezuela and Ecuador (1/7) and one species was also found in Russia Far East. The monophyly of the tribe has not been tested yet and it is doubtful. The genus *Ubychia* Rost, 1893 is a widespread genus of the anophthalmous and endogean weevils which currently contains 11 species and 2 subspecies (Morrone & Hlaváč 2017, Hlaváč & Nakládal 2018, Davidian, Arzanov & Chumachenko 2020). All palaearctic genera of the tribe are found in the Mediterranean region. The only

exception are *Ubychia* which go to Alps on the west and to northern Turkey, Caucasus and the Caspic region of Iran on the east.

The aim of this paper is the description of two new species of *Ubychia*, which gives important supplement information on the distribution of the genus, one is even extending it to the region of southern Carpathians.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Adult specimens were examined with a Leica S8APO stereomicroscope with diffuse lighting at magnifications up to 128x. Dry mounted specimens were relaxed in warm water and dissected; aedeagi were macerated in KOH solution, embedded in Euparal and illustrated. All dissected parts were mounted on plastic cards and pinned together with the respective specimen. Illustrated structures were studied with a ZEISS stereoscopic microscope and figured using a camera lucida.

The terminology of the rostrum and the genitalia follows Oberprieler (2014). The head length was measured from the anterior margin of the pronotum (base of head capsule) to the anterior margin of the rostrum; the elytral length was measured along the suture; the width refers to the maximum width of head, pronotum and elytra. The body length is the combined length of the head, pronotum and elytra, measured separately.

Label data of the holotype and paratypes are quoted verbatim, with slashes (/) separating lines on the label. All type specimens were provided with the following red printed label: HOLOTYPE or PARATYPE, *UBYCHIA* and specific name of the taxon, P. Hlaváč det., 2022.

The material is deposited in the following collections:

CNHM – Croatian Natural History Museum, Zagreb

PCDC – Private collection of Daniel Čáha, Prague, Czech Republic

PCPH – Private collection of Peter Hlaváč, Prague, Czech Republic

PCJB – Private collection of Jiří Brestovanský, Neratovice, Czech Republic

TAXONOMY

Ubychia jansai sp. n. Figs 1, 3–4

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Holotype: ♂, CROATIA: with two labels: “CROATIA, Lokve env. / Park šuma Golubinjak / Golubinja polušpilja (cave) / 30.9.–1.10.2017 / Brestovanský, Čáha & Jansa lgt.” [white, printed], “45°21’18”N / 14°45’57”E,

Fig. 1. *Ubychia jansai* sp. n., habitus (slightly immature specimen).

Fig. 2. *Ubychia romanica* sp. n., habitus.

cca 753 m / under the stones and sifting in the cave entrance" [white, printed] (CNHM). Paratypes (3 exx): 2 exx: same data as for holotype (PCJB, PCPH). 1ex: the same locality, but collected on 11.11.2023 (PCDC).

DIAGNOSIS. Body glabrous, shiny, light reddish-brown; head capsule globular, major part embedded in pronotum; eyes completely absent; distance between antennal insertion and posterior margin of rostrum about 2.5 times superior to distance to anterior margin of rostrum; antennal funicle hexamerous; scape pedunculate, about 1.3 times as long as funicle; pronotum unevenly, sparsely punctate, maximum width in middle of pronotal length; elytra elongate, slightly rounded at sides, about 1.65–1.70 times as long as wide, humeri well-defined, protruding with sharp tooth; anterior metaventral process wide, slightly convex; protibia toothless, outer margin slightly rounded.

DESCRIPTION. Body (Fig. 1) glabrous, shiny, light reddish-brown; antennae and

legs of same colour; length 2.02–2.16 mm, maximum elytral width 0.64–0.70 mm. Head capsule globular, major part embedded in pronotum. Eyes completely absent. Rostrum long, almost parallel-sided, with two parallel lines of fine punctures, decently downcurved, confluent with head capsule, dorsal constriction separating head capsule from neck region evanescent; antennal sockets invisible in dorsal view; rostrum expanded above antennal insertions, distance between antennal insertion and posterior margin of rostrum about 2.5 times superior to distance to anterior margin of rostrum; scrobe in lateral view long, reaching head capsule. Antennae with hexamerous funicle; scape pedunculate, about 1.3 times as long as funicle, antennomere 2 about 1.5 times as long as 3; antennomeres 3–5 and 6–7 subequal in length, 6–7 slightly longer than 3–5; about as long as wide or slightly transverse; antennomere 6–7 clearly transverse; antennal club (fused antennomeres 8–11) clearly longer than 3–7 combined.

Pronotum about 1.00–1.15 times as long as wide; unevenly, sparsely punctate, distance between punctures variable, more times of diameter of puncture; punctures on sides larger and denser; anterior margin slightly convex, sides evenly rounded, maximum width in middle of pronotal length.

Elytra elongate, slightly rounded at sides, about 1.65–1.70 times as long as wide, slightly more than twice as long as pronotum; with unevenly distributed, fine punctures and setae, humeri with well-defined, protruding with sharp tooth.

Mesoventrite about as long as metaventrite. All coxae widely separated; anterior metaventral process wide, slightly convex, confluent with posterior mesoventral process; first tergite with dense, strong punctures in anterior third, sparser in middle and disappearing in posterior third. First abdominal ventrite very long, about 2.8 times as long as ventrites 2–4 combined. All legs flat. Femora edentate, with well-developed interlocking ridges. Protibia toothless, outer margin slightly rounded; mesotibia with tooth in anterior third; metatibia with tooth in about middle; outer margin of meso and metatibiae in posterior part behind tooth with strong dense setae.

Male terminalia (Figs 2–3) with very long tegmen, only slightly shorter than median lobe, manubrium almost as long as temones; parameres fused to form one large, long, semitriangular lobe; median lobe slightly shorter than temones, with round apex.

Female terminalia not studied.

SEXUAL DIMORPHISM. First abdominal ventrite in male with well-defined medium impression, flat in females.

REMARKS. *Ubychia jansai* sp. n. has hexamerous funicle. This character is shared between *U. leonhardi* Reitter, 1914 (Italy – Lombardia, Switzerland – Ticino); *U. jansai* sp. n. (Croatia – Gorski Kotar); *U. salpingoides* (Kraatz, 1881) (Croatia, Montenegro, BiH); *U. ellipsoidalis* Osella & Nonveiller, 1982 (Serbia, BiH); *U.*

Figs 3-4 *Ubychia jansai* sp. n., aedeagus: **3**. lateral view;
4. dorsal view. Scale 0.2 mm.

romanica sp. n. (Romania – southern Carpathians)); *U. holdhausi* (Ganglbauer, 1903) (BiH, Serbia); *U. reitteri* Ganglbauer, 1906 (Greece – Corfu, Epiros) and *U. mingrelica* (Reitter, 1894) (Georgia, Turkey, Iran, Russia – Krasnodarskiy kray). *U. jansai* sp. n. is closely related to *U. leonhardi* sharing with late protibiae lacking tooth on outer margin, but it differs from by the different structure of the aedeagus.

NATURAL HISTORY. All four specimens of the type serie were collected under stones or by the sifting in the cave entrance.

ETYMOLOGY. Named after my friend, very enthusiastic Curculionidae lover and one of the collectors of the type serie, Petr Jansa (Hradec Králové, Czech Republic).

DISTRIBUTION. Croatia (Gorski Kotar)

Ubychia romanica sp. n. Figs 2, 5-7

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Holotype: ♂, ROMANIA: with two labels: “ROMANIA, jud. Vilcea, Sub- / Carpații Vâlci, 1 km ESE / Sîmboțin, valley to Snamâna, / stream at erosive hills, 340 m“ [white, printed], “bottom of eroded wall, soil- / washing 5 to 30 cm deep [646] / 45°10'16"N, 24°23'31"E / 28.III.2019, Gy. Makranczy & T. Struyve lgt.” [white, printed] (PCPH). Paratypes (1♂): same data as for holotype (PCPH).

DIAGNOSIS. Body glabrous, shiny, dark reddish-brown; head capsule globular, major part embedded in pronotum; eyes completely absent; distance between antennal insertion and posterior margin of rostrum about three times superior to distance to anterior margin of rostrum. Antennal funicle hexamerous; scape pedunculate, about 1.1 times as long as funicle; pronotum evenly, sparsely punctate, punctures on sides strong, maximum width in middle of pronotal length; elytra elongate, slightly rounded at sides, about 1.65–1.70 times as long as wide; protibia with well-defined medium tooth on outer margin.

DESCRIPTION. Body (Fig. 2) glabrous, shiny, dark reddish-brown; antennae and legs of same colour; length 2.38–2.64 mm, maximum elytral width 0.70–0.82 mm.

Head capsule globular, major part embedded in pronotum. Eyes completely absent. Rostrum long, parallel-sided, with two parallel lines of fine punctures, decently downcurved, almost confluent with head capsule, dorsal constriction separating head capsule from neck region evanescent; antennal sockets invisible in dorsal view; rostrum expanded above antennal insertions, distance between antennal insertion and posterior margin of rostrum about three superior to distance to anterior margin of rostrum; scrobe in lateral view long, reaching head capsule. Antennae with hexamerous funicle; scape pedunculate, about 1.1 times as long as funicle, antennomere 2 about 1.5 times as long as 3; antennomeres 3–7 subequal,

Figs 5-7. *Ubychia romanica* sp. n.: 5, aedeagus lateral view; 6, aedeagus, dorsal view; 7, spiculum gastrale. Scale 0.2 mm.

about as long as wide or slightly transverse; antennomere 6 clearly transverse; antennal club (fused antennomeres 8-11) clearly longer than 3-7 combined.

Pronotum evenly, sparsely punctate, punctures on sides strong, distance between punctures 2-3 times of diameter of puncture; about 1.2-1.3 times as long as wide; anterior margin slightly convex, sides evenly rounded, maximum width in middle of pronotal length.

Mesoventrite about twice as long as metaventrite. All coxae widely separated; posterior mesoventral process truncate, confluent with anterior metaventral process. First abdominal ventrite with sparse, unevenly distributed strong punctures in anterior half, disappearing in posterior half, very long, about 2.8 times as long as ventrites 2-4 combined.

Elytra elongate, slightly rounded at sides, about 1.65-1.70 times as long as wide, almost twice as long as pronotum; with unevenly distributed, fine punctures.

All legs flat. Femora edentate, with well-developed interlocking ridges. Protibia with well-defined medium tooth on outer margin; mesotibia with tooth behind anterior third; metatibia with tooth in posterior third; outer margin of meso- and metatibiae in posterior part behind tooth with strong dense setae.

Male terminalia with sternite IX (Fig. 7, *spiculum gastrale*) symmetrical, basal arms slender with outer margin in posterior half dentate, strongly divergent. Aedeagus (Figs 5-6) with tegmen moderately long, strongly curved in distal part; parameres fused to form one large and wide lobe; length of manubrium about two third of length of temones; median lobe moderately short, about half the length of temones, with truncate apex.

Female terminalia not studied.

SEXUAL DIMORPHISM. First abdominal ventrite in male with well-defined medium impression, flat in females.

REMARKS. *Ubychia romanica* sp. n. has also hexamerous funicle; it is most closely related to *U. salpingoides* by sharing the following set of characters 1) elytra oblong oval, with fine, uneven punctures, 2) punctation on the whole surface of the pronotum strong, same and 3) body size under 2.7 mm. *Ubychia romanica* sp. n. differs from *U. salpingoides* by larger size of the body, much stronger punctation of pronotum which has its maximum width in middle.

NATURAL HISTORY. Both type specimens were collected by soil washing near a stream on the bottom of an eroded wall at erosive hills in the altitude of 340 m a.s.l.

ETYMOLOGY. Named after Romania, the country of its discovery.

Distribution. Romania (southern Carpathians)

Fig. 8. Distribution of *Ubychia* species in the Balkans.

Fig. 9. Distribution of the genus *Ubychia*.

Key to species of *Ubychia* (with hexamerous antennal funicle) of the Balkan Peninsula

(Osella 1977, edited and expanded)

- 1 Protibiae edentate, slightly rounded on outer margin ... 2
 - Protibiae on outer margin with well-defined medium tooth ... 3
- 2 Aedeagus truncate at apex. Italy: Lombardia, Switzerland: Ticino ...
 - ... *U. leonhardi* Reitter
 - Aedeagus rounded at apex. Croatia: Gorski Kotar ... *U. jansai* sp. n.
- 3 Elytra in medium third almost parallel-sided, having shape of bottle. Punctures on elytral disc strong, forming well-defined 2–3 striae. Greece: Corfu and Epiros ...
 - ... *U. reitteri* Ganglbauer
 - Elytra oblong oval. Elytral disc with fine, uneven punctures, lacking striae ... 4
- 4 Punctuation of pronotum variable, lateral portions with strong, dense punctures, disc of pronotum with fine, sparse punctures. Bosnia and Hercegovina, Serbia ...
 - ... *U. holdhausi* (Ganglbauer)
 - Punctuation of pronotum on whole surface fine or strong, but always same. ... 5
- 5 Large species, body length about 3 mm. Serbia, Bosnia and Hercegovina: Republic of Serbia ...
 - ... *U. ellipsoidalis* (Ganglbauer)
 - Small species, body length less than 2.7 mm ... 6
- 6 Body length about 1.8–2.0 mm. Pronotum evenly, finely punctate; maximum width of pronotum in posterior third. Croatia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Hercegovina: Dalmatia ...
 - ... *U. salpingoides* (Kraatz)
 - Body length about 2.4–2.6 mm. Pronotum evenly, stronger punctate, maximum width of pronotum in middle. Romania: southern Carpathians ... *U. romanica* sp. n.

DISCUSSION

The biogeography and the distribution of *Ubychia* was discussed in detail and, at that time, all known records of the genus were provided and mapped by Hlaváč and Nakládal (2018) for eleven species and two subspecies. Since the date of this publication, only one, but very important contribution on *Ubychia* of Caucasus has been published (Davidian, Arzanov & Chumachenko 2020). The authors described the species *Ubychia abagoensis* Davidian & Arzanov, 2020 from Adygea. They also reported *Ubychia mingrelica* (Reitter, 1894) for the first time from western Caucasus (Krasnodarsky kray, Russia) and synonymized *Ubychia solochau* Struyve, 2010 with *Ubychia stygia* Rost, 1893.

New species which are described here are important from the biogeographical point of view of the genus. *Ubychia jansai* sp. n. from Gorski Kotar (northern Velebit) which had been already reported by Hlaváč and Nakládal (2018) is partly

filling the gap between the isolated population of *Ubychia leonhardi* Reitter, 1914 from northern Italy (Lombardia) and Switzerland (Ticino) and *Ubychia* species distributed in Croatia, Montenegro and Bosnia and Hercegovina. The finding of *Ubychia romanica* sp. n. in southern Carpathians in Romania is extending the distribution range of the European members of the genus out of the mediterranean region. Records of undescribed *Ubychia* in North Macedonia and southern Turkey (Figs 8, 9, *question mark*) remains unconfirmed. The presence of *Ubychia ganglbaueri* in central Bosnia and Hercegovina also needs the confirmation by new finding. No doubt, that more collecting effort will bring more information of the distribution and certainly also another new species of *Ubychia*, especially in Greece and Caucasus.

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